

Examination & Assignment

Welcome to our Workshop!

GJU / HS Magdeburg-Stendal

8.2.22 15:00 – 18:00

Dr. Stefan Vörtler

Agenda

Program for today

“Entry” to the topic

Challenges and Problems observed – Change of Perspective

Preparation of exams >> Administration >> Grading

Function of Exams

Alignment to the learning outcomes

Taxonomy of learning outcomes

Practical application of the taxonomy

--- Flexible Block to your topics ---

Conflicts & Problems with exams

Challenge/ Problems of Exams

- grading
- wording >>> open exams, not multiple choice; length & precision of the answers
- knowledge >>> and its testing; application, evaluation, creation
- arrangement simple to more difficult questions/topics
- learning outcomes in mind
- time >>> duration of the exam >>> 1 point/ 1 min in answer
- “test theory” >>> psychology has theories, models, suggestions
- level of exam in context of modul(study program
- covering of topics >>> all or just a few, but these to very much details
- anxiety // frustration >>> motivation & support
- understanding different >>> wrong concepts / thoughts with students
- formative assessment set-up
- common understanding

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Preparing Exams: Challenges

Change of Perspektive

Which **Problems** // **Challenges** do you know or observe in the context of examinations ...

- ... with the view of the **Examinees / Students**
- ... with the view of the **Examiners / Instructors?**

Discuss your ideas/finding >> exchange with your peers >> group/cluster them

Group discussion ~**15'** >> presentation in plenum

WHY do we do Exams? (Functions)

1. Selection

- based on knowledge
- “ranking” of students
- Recruitment
- Prognostic function to future employments

3. Didactics

- Structuring the field of study
- test of knowledge
- Motivation & Reward
- Result/outcome as feedback
- Feedback to stud. & docent
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- Examples: Medical, Law exam; Entry to certain professions
 - Entry to certain “groups”/communities: MBA for business leader
 - kind of exam reflects “entry ritual”: clinical exams 18 tests/3 wks

2. Initiation // Access

Constructive Alignment

xyz

Taxonomy

(Following Bloom)

Verbalizations

(Bloom's Taxonomy Learning Activities and Assessments. Centre for Teaching Excellence, University of Waterloo)

Verbalizations: detailed verbs

(Foundation Online Learning (UK) - <https://www.foundationonline.org.uk/> - Teacher Planning Kit)

Verbalizations: detailed verbs

HIGH LEVEL THINKING SKILLS

Analysis

To *examine* in detail. Examining and breaking information into parts by identifying motives or causes; making inferences and finding evidence to support generalisations.

Key words:

Analyse	Examine	Prioritize
Appraise	Find	Question
Arrange	Focus	Rank
Assumption	Function	Reason
Breakdown	Group	Relationships
Categorise	Highlight	Reorganise
Cause and effect	In-depth discussion	Research
Choose	Inference	See
Classify	Inspect	Select
Differences	Investigate	Separate
Discover	Isolate	Similar to
Discriminate	List	Simplify
Dissect	Motive	Survey
Distinction	Omit	Take part in
Distinguish	Order	Test for
Divide	Organise	Theme
Establish	Point out	Comparing

Synthesis

To *change* or *create* into something new. Compiling information together in a different way by combining elements in a new pattern or proposing alternative solutions.

Key words:

Adapt	Estimate	Plan
Add to	Experiment	Predict
Build	Extend	Produce
Change	Formulate	Propose
Choose	Happen	Reframe
Combine	Hypothesise	Revise
Compile	Imagine	Rewrite
Compose	Improve	Simplify
Construct	Innovate	Solve
Convert	Integrate	Speculate
Create	Invent	Substitute
Delete	Make up	Suppose
Design	Maximise	Tabulate
Develop	Minimise	Test
Devise	Model	Theorise
Discover	Modify	Think
Discuss	Original	Transform
Elaborate	Originate	Visualise

Evaluation

To *justify*. Presenting and defending opinions by making judgements about information, validity of ideas or quality of work based on a set of criteria.

Key words:

Agree	Disprove	Measure
Appraise	Dispute	Opinion
Argue	Effective	Perceive
Assess	Estimate	Persuade
Award	Evaluate	Prioritise
Bad	Explain	Prove
Choose	Give reasons	Rate
Compare	Good	Recommend
Conclude	Grade	Rule on
Consider	How do we know?	Select
Convince	Importance	Support
Criteria	Infer	Test
Criticise	Influence	Useful
Debate	Interpret	Validate
Decide	Judge	Value
Deduct	Justify	Why
Defend	Mark	
Determine		

(Foundation Online Learning (UK) - <https://www.foundationonline.org.uk/> - Teacher Planning Kit)

Verbalizations: detailed questions

Actions:	Outcomes:	Actions:	Outcomes:	Actions:	Outcomes:
Describing	Definition	Classifying	Collection	Carrying out	Demonstration
Finding	Fact	Comparing	Examples	Executing	Diary
Identifying	Label	Exemplifying	Explanation	Implementing	Illustrations
Listing	List	Explaining	Label	Using	Interview
Locating	Quiz	Inferring	List		Journal
Naming	Reproduction	Interpreting	Outline		Performance
Recognising	Test	Paraphrasing	Quiz		Presentation
Retrieving	Workbook	Summarising	Show and tell		Sculpture
	Worksheet		Summary		Simulation
Questions:		Questions:		Questions:	
Can you list three ...?		Can you explain what is happening . . . what is meant . . .?		How would you use...?	
Can you recall ...?		How would you classify the type of ...?		What examples can you find to ...?	
Can you select ...?		How would you compare ...?contrast ...?		How would you solve _____ using what you have learned ...?	
How did _____ happen?		How would you rephrase the meaning ...?		How would you organise _____ to show ...?	
How is ...?		How would you summarise ...?		How would you show your understanding of ...?	
How would you describe ...?		What can you say about ...?		What approach would you use to...?	
How would you explain ...?		What facts or ideas show ...?		How would you apply what you learned to develop ...?	
How would you show ...?		What is the main idea of ...?		What other way would you plan to ...?	
What is ...?		Which is the best answer ...?		What would result if ...?	
When did ...?		Which statements support ...?		Can you make use of the facts to ...?	
When did _____ happen?		Will you state or interpret in your own words ...?		What elements would you choose to change ...?	
Where is . . . ?				What facts would you select to show ...?	
Which one ...?				What questions would you ask in an interview with ...?	
Who was ...?					
Who were the main . . . ?					
Why did ...?					

(Foundation Online Learning (UK) - <https://www.foundationonline.org.uk/> - Teacher Planning Kit)

Verbalizations: detailed questions

Actions:

Attributing
Deconstructing
Integrating
Organising
Outlining
Structuring

Outcomes:

Abstract
Chart
Checklist
Database
Graph
Mobile
Report
Spread sheet
Survey

Actions:

Constructing
Designing
Devising
Inventing
Making
Planning
Producing

Outcomes:

Advertisement
Film
Media product
New game
Painting
Plan
Project
Song
Story

Actions:

Attributing
Checking
Deconstructing
Integrating
Organising
Outlining
Structuring

Outcomes:

Abstract
Chart
Checklist
Database
Graph
Mobile
Report
Spread sheet
Survey

Questions:

What are the parts or features of ...?
How is _____ related to ...?
Why do you think ...?
What is the theme ...?
What motive is there ...?
Can you list the parts ...?
What inference can you make ...?
What conclusions can you draw ...?
How would you classify ...?
How would you categorise ...?
Can you identify the difference parts ...?
What evidence can you find ...?
What is the relationship between ...?
Can you make a distinction between ...?
What is the function of ...?
What ideas justify ...?

Questions:

What changes would you make to solve...?
How would you improve ...?
What would happen if...?
Can you elaborate on the reason...?
Can you propose an alternative...?
Can you invent...?
How would you adapt _____ to create a different...?
How could you change (modify) the plot (plan)...?
What could be done to minimise (maximise)...?
What way would you design...?
Suppose you could _____ what would you do...?
How would you test...?
Can you formulate a theory for...?
Can you predict the outcome if...?
How would you estimate the results for...?
What facts can you compile...?
Can you construct a model that would change...?
Can you think of an original way for the ...?

Questions:

Do you agree with the actions/outcomes...?
What is your opinion of...?
How would you prove/disprove...?
Can you assess the value/importance of...?
Would it be better if...?
Why did they (the character) choose...?
What would you recommend...?
How would you rate the...?
What would you cite to defend the actions...?
How would you evaluate ...?
How could you determine...?
What choice would you have made...?
What would you select...?
How would you prioritise...?
What judgement would you make about...?
Based on what you know, how would you explain...?
What information would you use to support the view...?
How would you justify...?
What data was used to make the conclusion...?

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Teacher Planning Kit)

Example: Application of verbalizations – matrix design for examiners Documentation & fast grading with test

Sprachenzentrum
Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

UNicer®
Mündliche Prüfung

Sprache: _____

Name: _____ Vorname: _____ Geburtsdatum: _____

Fragen/Themen

Ad-hoc-Bewertung des Prüfers/Zweitprüfers

	1	2	3	4	5
Aussprache					
Formale Strukturen					
Wortschatz					
Flüssigkeit					
Gesprächsführung					

Die Ad-hoc-Markierungen des Prüfers/Zweitprüfers dienen als Grundlage für die Endbewertung.

Endbewertung

Note Bewertung	1 / 1,3 (sehr gut)	1,7/2,0/2,3 (gut)	2,7/3,0/3,3 (befriedigend)	3,7/4,0 (ausreichend)	4,7 / 5 (nicht ausreichend)	Note
Aussprache (Intonation, Phonetik)	sauber, sehr gut verständlich	kleinere Mängel, gut verständlich	nicht immer- sauber, einige Mängel	deutliche Mängel, oft unverständlich	kaum verständlich	
Formale Strukturen, Grammatik	fehlerfrei, sehr gute Kenntnis der Form	Unsicherheiten im marginalen Bereich	Unsicherheiten und Fehler im formalen Kernbereich	Systematische Unsicherheiten in manchen Bereichen	Häufige Regelverstöße in vielen Bereichen	
Wortschatz & Register	volle Ausnutzung des vorhandenen Wortschatzes	fast durchweg fehlerfreie, angemessene Ausdrucksweise	kleinere Lücken im Wortschatz	deutliche Lücken im Wortschatz	Wortschatz nicht ausreichend	
Flüssigkeit	spricht flüssig	kleine Zäsuren, aber homogen	längere Zäsuren	unsicher, mit einigen Selbst- korrekturen	stockend, mit längeren Pausen	
Gesprächs- führung	gewandt redesteuernd	folgt gut dem Gesprächsfaden, ohne jedoch Eigeninitiative zu zeigen	kleine Hilfe des Prüfers notwendig	defensive Haltung, ist immer wieder auf Fragen angewiesen	Gespräch kommt kaum zustande	
Gesamtnote						

Gespräch: Note _____

Hörverstehen: Note _____

Gesamtnote *Mündliche Prüfung*: _____ (_____)

Erlangen, Unterschrift Prüfer

Unterschrift Zweitprüfer